

Research Article

PIQUE-NIQUE MATT

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Abstract: *When having a picnic in nature, by rivers or beaches, tourists frequently struggle to carry a large number of necessities. As a result, there would be landfills on the riverbank and along the shores. In natural areas such as beaches and rivers, it is difficult to find dumpsters close by. Therefore, the innovative "Pique-Nique Matt" picnic mat with multiple compartments was created. This product is a picnic mat that incorporates the novel concept of adding storage compartments for picnic essentials made from sustainable materials, such as a laundry net bag, foldable trash bin, handmade tissue cover, sewing, and a reusable picnic mat, which promotes environmental cleanliness and pollution protection. The product includes compostable plastic bags for littering. The product is user-friendly and portable, featuring a sling strap, a foldable mat, and a lightweight construction. The product is user-friendly due to its portability, which allows the user to carry it anywhere and at any time. The product is advantageous to society because the community can practise preventing water pollution. This innovation's primary objective is to expose the concept of innovation and the structure of the product to be introduced in the commercialization field at a reasonable price. No marketers or innovators in the global market have developed this kind of product. The product can be used in places like nature preserves, beaches, and riverbanks that people visit.*

Keywords: Pique-Nique Matt; touristic product; recycle; innovation; sustainable

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1. INTRODUCTION

Tourism is defined as spending time away from home in pursuit of leisure, relaxation, and pleasure while utilising the commercial provision of services. Therefore, despite having roots in classical antiquity, tourism is a byproduct of contemporary social structures that emerged in 17th-century western Europe (Walton, 2022). The upcoming generation will likely have a substantial population on the planet. As evidenced by a single observation, the large population of humans on this planet has spawned an abundance of tourism-related businesses that have a significant positive impact on governments, businesses, and locals (Gondos, 2014). The company's sustainable activities will contribute to long-term profitability and economic stability (Mollenkap, 2022). Future practises that businesses may adopt must be forward-thinking. Supporting and caring for the environment, the bottom line, and people's surroundings requires taking into account and incorporating multiple points of view. In the midst of development, one principle is strictly adhered to: the preservation of the existing environment. Typically, large corporations deceive visitors by claiming their products are environmentally friendly. Instead of considering potential repercussions that could affect the overall

aspects, almost all businesses agree to increase profits. Large corporations have adopted nature-based concepts as a result of the numerous sustainable measures taken to preserve the veracity of the green concept and physical preservation. In addition, they engage in additional activities to maintain a stable profit for their exclusive corporate enterprise. Sustainable tourism, according to Inchainge (2022), focuses on the triple bottom line by incorporating the three Ps: profit (economic impacts), planet (environmental impacts), and people (impacts on the local residents). Sustainable activities have made the tourism industry better, and putting sustainable ideas into practise in the tourism industry has changed the environment, community, and economy of the country.

Foreign earnings via exports, enterprise, jobs, income, and financial systems are the primary economic effects of sustainable tourism (Coastlane, 2018). First, export-based foreign earnings have contributed to the host economy's profit growth. The export and import of related goods and services generate revenue for the host country. The author further added that tourism is the primary source of foreign exchange earnings for at least 38% of all countries, according to World Bank research.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

As part of the product's formation process, sewing is utilised. The compartments are sewn by hand onto the picnic blanket. All of the materials used in the innovations are eco-friendly. The items consist of a reusable laundry net bag, a foldable cotton trash bin, a handmade cotton tissue cover, a sewing kit, and a reusable picnic mat. In addition, a hook is attached to the laundry net bag so that it can be folded when not being used to store plates and silverware. The materials pertain to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), which are innovation (SDG9), addressing climate change (SDG13), protecting life on land (SDG14), and protecting life under the sea (SDG15).

3. FINDINGS

A feasibility survey was distributed to the community and society in order to obtain feedback on the acceptance of the product innovation. Based on data obtained from a Google Form survey, the results are shown as pie charts and bar graphs that show every aspect of the demographic profile, previous picnic experience, and real opinions about "Pique-Nique Matt".

3.1 Demographic Profile

The demographic profiles of the respondents are presented in Section A. The main channel for distribution to 130 respondents was a Google form questionnaire. The demographic results from Section A show that the majority of respondents (53.8%) were aged 22-26, and the majority of respondents (84.6%) were Malay. The findings also reveal that the majority of students (50.8%) are STPM/Degree (51.5%).

3.2 Previous Picnic Experience

Section B focuses on the previous picnic experiences of the respondents. According to our survey, 52.2% of respondents indicated that they often attend picnics. The majority of respondents (59.6%) bring two to three bags and 72.8% bring their own tissue while picnicking. According to 67.7% of respondents, locating a trash can near the picnic area is difficult. In addition, 39.7% of respondents bring their cutlery and plates in reusable bags, and 90.4% agree that it is difficult to bring a large quantity of utensils when bags have limited compartments. Consequently, 97.1% of respondents like

the idea of adding a compartment to the picnic blanket so that it is easier to bring plates, cutlery, tissue, and trash bags.

3.3 *Pique-Nique Matt User Acceptance*

The correspondence response to the acceptance idea for the innovation product "Pique-Nique Matt" is discussed in Section C. At 83.5%, the majority rules for not having found a product similar to "Pique-Nique Matt" on the market. Conversely, 88.7% of respondents concur that the product is convenient for them. 92.5 percent of respondents agreed that the "Pique-Nique Matt" is a suitable place for a trash bag, and 97.7 percent liked the idea of compartments on the mat. Also, 96.2% of those who answered think that the "Pique-Nique Matt" fits their tastes, and 70.7% of those who answered would buy it.

4. DISCUSSION ON PRODUCT FEATURES

The innovative product features a compartment on the picnic mat's open side with a foldable trash can on the upper left, a laundry net bag in the upper centre, and a tissue cover on the upper right. On the picnic blanket, all of the eco-friendly materials are sewn together. Also, when the product is folded, there is a black storage net sewn into the back of the product.

4.1 *Product Design*

Figure 1. **Front View**

Figure 2. **Side view**

Figure 3. **Back views**

Figure 4. **Open matt view**

4.2 *Uniqueness*

Our product is distinctive in that it has numerous compartments attached to the mat itself. "Pique-Nique Matt" was created to prevent its users from bringing a large number of bags to their desired picnic locations. Consequently, our product can be folded into a sling bag as an alternative to being carried by hand. "Pique-Nique Matt" also provides ample storage space for essentials such as silverware, toilet paper, a trash bag, and a trash can. We also provide compostable trash bags for the users, making it easier for them to collect trash before depositing it in a nearby trash can or to keep the bags until they find a trash can. The compostable trash bags we used can decompose into compost, a high-quality organic fertiliser that is also great for the environment.

4.3 *Usefulness*

The compartment in the "Pique-Nique Matt" and the compostable trash bag can help the user keep the environment clean by picking up trash, as well as make it easier for the user to carry only one bag to the picnic, making it a portable product that can be brought anywhere, at any time. The first compartment, a recycled laundry net bag, is used to store cutlery and plates, allowing the user to carry all of their essentials in a single bag. The second compartment added to the picnic blanket itself is a handcrafted tissue holder. The tissue box cover is made of fabric, which can be reused. As individuals occasionally forget to bring tissues to the picnic, the tissue holder serves to hold the tissues. The third compartment is a collapsible trash can that encourages the user to use the provided compostable trash bag. Because it has shoulder straps, the "Pique-Nique Matt" is easily transportable. Aside from that, this innovative product is foldable and requires minimal storage space.

4.4 *Commercialization*

According to the survey results, the commercialization of the "Pique-Nique Matt" innovation product is in high demand among potential consumers and tourists. The price of the tourist products is affordable. Both low- and high-income earners were able to acquire the "Pique-Nique Matt". In addition, the "Pique-Nique Matt" is designed to appeal to all age groups and genders. The "Pique-Nique Matt" targeted families, groups, and students, as they frequently travel to natural areas and beaches for vacations and holidays. Moreover, the product contains components that support the Sustainable Development Goals: innovation (SDG9), climate action (SDG13), life below water (SDG14), and life on land (SDG15).

5. CONCLUSION

Tourism is unquestionably an excellent field in which society can engage in activities for calm, leisure, and relaxation; spend quality time with family, friends, and relatives; and even engage in business travel. However, eco-friendly and sustainable products diminish the similarities between humans and nature. World Health Organization-invented reuse, recycle, and reduction elements are incorporated into the product's material usage, resulting in product benefits (WHO). By utilising recycled and reusable materials, for instance, the product's price is reduced. Those interested in innovative products like "Pique-Nique Matt." Before making a purchase in the modern world, a significant number of individuals consider a product's sustainable materials. The use of green materials is currently available on the market, and their purpose of protecting Mother Nature from harmful human actions is increasing their demand. Therefore, "Pique-Nique Matt" has significant market potential among potential consumers. In the end, "Pique-Nique Matt" has the right qualities to be put on the market for tourists and consumers to use while keeping the environment safe.

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